

FORUM FOR
INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH
IN MEDICAL SCIENCE &
TECHNOLOGY

FIRMST 2020 | Moscow | Conference Abstracts

clinical research and work that requires an increased level of competence and a greater depth of knowledge.

Following the interviews of two principal researchers a list of the main requirements for nursing personnel involved in research has been compiled.

These requirements include:

1. Controlling and informing the investigating physician about the presence (arrival) of a suitable patient in the hospital.
2. Maintenance of non-medical documentation (questionnaires / brochures / checklists)
3. Accurate and complete execution of appointments in accordance with the research protocol (there are situations when the number of participating personnel is not able to ensure the execution of all appointments on time, which casts doubt on the correctness of the research)
4. Careful documentation of any and all of events occurring with patients in the study
5. To observe discipline and coordination (disclosure of inaccurate information, misleading the patient, etc.)
6. Control of delivery of the investigational drug to the facility (if the investigator / organization require such)
7. Full awareness of the subject of research, the principles of its work and other requirements.
8. Assistance to the physician in maintaining documentation, if the level of competence permits.

WHAT'S HAPPENING WITH E-CIGARETTES IN IRELAND?

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Introduction: E-cigarette use has increased rapidly worldwide since 2013 and there have been worrying increases in the use of e-cigarettes by adolescents and young people. In Ireland, smoking prevalence has declined significantly in recent decades but the availability of e-cigarettes in Ireland in recent years has led to

concerns about the Tobacco Endgame. We examine changes in e-cigarette use among 15-16 year olds in Ireland between 2015 and 2019.

Materials and Methods: We use data from 2 waves (2015, 1,472 students and 2019, 1,949 students) of the Irish wing of the European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD), a cross-sectional survey that, every four years, collects comparable data on substance use among European students aged 15 and 16 years, including on e-cigarette use.

Results: More students report using e-cigarettes in 2019 than in 2015, and the use of e-cigarettes among students is now more common than cigarette

FIRMST

4-5 Aug 2020 | Moscow

The
Physician
Journal of The British Association of Physicians of Indian Origin

Physicianjnl.net

Journal of International Health

Conference Abstracts

smoking. In 2019, almost four in 10 students (39%) had tried e-cigarettes and almost one in 6 (16%) were current users, up from 23% and 10% respectively in 2015. In 2019, boys (46%) were more likely than girls (33%) to have tried e-cigarettes and also to be current users (22% vs 12%). When asked about their reasons for trying e-cigarettes, about two-thirds (63%, 66%) said that it was "out of curiosity" in both 2015 and 2019, and 21% and 29% respectively said that it was because their friends offered it. In 2015, 17% said that it was to quit smoking while in 2019, only 3% gave that reason. Asked about their tobacco use when they first used an e-cigarette, in 2015 33% had never smoked tobacco but this had doubled to 68% in 2019.

Conclusion : E-cigarette use among 15-16 year olds in Ireland has increased more than 50% between 2015 and 2019, with boys more at risk than girls. Of particular concern is the significant increase in the numbers of young people using e-cigarettes who have never smoked tobacco. Policy and legislative implications include provision of health education for young people about e-cigarettes, consideration of e-cigarette cessation programmes for adolescents, and the extension of tobacco control legislation regarding minors to be extended to include e-cigarettes.

Keywords: E-cigarettes, tobacco control, adolescents, health education, trend

year-olds has been reducing over the last 25 years and we need to monitor smoking in young people to see if we can eradicate smoking in youth.

Methods: In May 2019 using pen and paper and the standardised ESPAD survey instrument we surveyed a stratified random sample of 1949 students born in 2003. 49% were male and 51% were female.

Results: 32% of respondents had tried smoking and 14% were current smokers, with 5% smoking daily. The majority (63%) of students reported starting to smoke at age 14 or 15. Access to cigarettes was reported as easy by 61% of students. Smoking was statistically significantly ($p=0.001$) associated with truancy and lower grades, perceived relative wealth, lower parental education, parental monitoring, rule setting, support, relationship with parents, peer smoking, alcohol, cannabis and other substance use. A trend analysis showed that, despite a reduction of over two-thirds since 1995 (the second largest decline of any of the seven major indicators of the ESPAD survey in Ireland), slightly more students reported smoking in 2019 than in 2015, and this was pronounced for boys. In Ireland, smoking among these 15-16-year olds was greatly reduced to 14% in 2019. This represents a reduction of over two-thirds (66%) since 1995.

Conclusions: While these results are encouraging the failure of prevalence to fall since 2015 is disappointing.